

Teacher And Student Factors on Optimism Among Academic Underachieving In-School Adolescents in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Optimism, the tendency to expect positive outcomes, plays a pivotal role in students' psychological well-being and academic persistence. Among academically underachieving adolescents, optimism can serve as a buffer against feelings of failure and low motivation. However, optimism is not developed in isolation; it is often influenced by teacher-related factors such as expectations and classroom management practices, as well as student-related variables including emotional intelligence, achievement motivation, gender, and age. Despite these theoretical linkages, there remains a dearth of empirical evidence on how teacher and student factors jointly influence optimism among academically underachieving adolescents in Nigeria. Therefore, this study investigates Teacher and Student factors on optimism among Academic underachieving in-school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria.

The study adopted a descriptive research design of correlational type. The population comprised all academically underachieving in-school adolescents in public secondary schools in Oyo State. Using a multistage sampling technique, 450 respondents were selected across six local government areas in Ibadan. The instrument include The Teacher Expectation Scale (TES) = 0.89, Teacher Classroom Management Scale = 0.87, Optimism Scale = 0.86, Emotional Intelligence Scale = 0.88 and Achievement Motivation Scale = 0.86. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analyses at a 0.05 level of significance.

The results shows that the level of optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria is moderate ($x=2.56$). Also, teacher expectation ($r = .680, p < 0.05$), teacher classroom management ($r = .279, p < 0.05$), emotional intelligence ($r = .276, p < 0.05$) and achievement motivation ($r = .226, p < 0.05$) was significantly and positively

correlated with optimism. Conversely, gender ($r = .033$, $p > .05$) and age ($r = .047$, $p > .05$) showed weak and non-significant correlations with optimism. All the variables jointly accounted for 54.1% in the prediction of optimism. Teacher expectation ($\beta = 0.653$, $p < 0.05$), teacher classroom ($\beta = 0.237$, $p < 0.05$) and ($\beta = 0.160$, $p < 0.05$) emotional intelligence contributed significantly and positively to optimism. However, achievement motivation ($\beta = -0.076$, $p > 0.05$), gender ($\beta = 0.067$, $p > 0.05$), and age ($\beta = -0.018$, $p > 0.05$) did not make statistically significant contributions to the prediction of optimism.

The study concluded that both teacher and student factors significantly influence optimism among academically underachieving in-school adolescents. The study recommends that teacher training programs incorporate strategies that foster supportive expectations and emotional development among students to enhance academic optimism and reduce underachievement.

Keywords: Optimism, Teacher Expectation, Classroom Management, Emotional Intelligence; Achievement Motivation, Gender, Age

Background to the Study

Academic underachievement among school adolescents continues to pose a major challenge in Nigeria's educational system, especially in states such as Oyo State where disparities in learning environments, socioeconomic conditions, and school resources directly impact learners' performance. Academic underachievement occurs when students perform significantly below their intellectual potential or expected grade level (Olatunji and Aremu, 2020). For many secondary school learners, this gap manifests in persistent failure in school subjects, difficulty completing academic tasks, poor test scores, and declining motivation. For instance, WAEC statistics over recent years have shown fluctuations in pass rates across subjects in Oyo State, highlighting concerns about students who repeatedly fall below expected achievement benchmarks.

A key psychological construct relevant to understanding how adolescents cope with academic challenges is optimism. Optimism refers to the general expectation that good things will happen in the future (Scheier and Carver, 2018). Studies have shown that optimistic adolescents tend to persevere longer in academic tasks, experience lower levels of stress, and adopt problem-focused coping strategies (Peterson, 2000). For an underachieving student who consistently fails mathematics, for example, a strong sense of optimism may motivate them to seek help, attend extra lessons, or attempt additional practice instead of giving up. Conversely, a pessimistic student may withdraw, avoid assignments, or assume improvement is impossible. Similarly, adolescents who exhibit higher levels of optimism are more likely to persevere in the face of setbacks, maintain intrinsic motivation, and approach academic tasks with confidence, even when they have previously struggled. Conversely, low levels of optimism may lead to negative self-perceptions, academic disengagement, and a sense of hopelessness, which can perpetuate

cycles of underachievement. Optimism, therefore, is not merely a personality trait but a critical psychosocial factor that can significantly influence the trajectory of an adolescent's educational experience and overall development (Gallagher, 2020; Putwain, Schunk, and Symes, 2022).

Optimism (defined as the general expectation that positive outcomes will occur) has been robustly linked to adaptive academic behaviours and better psychological adjustment among children and adolescents. Recent empirical work shows optimism predicts persistence, problem-focused coping, and lower emotional distress after academic setbacks: for example, longitudinal research found that higher dispositional optimism in early adolescence prospectively related to greater psychological wellbeing and lower future maladjustment, suggesting optimism helps students recover from setbacks rather than withdraw (Gallagher, 2020). Experimental and correlational studies also report that optimism interacts with academic self-efficacy to predict performance: students who report both high self-efficacy and optimism show the strongest gains in grades and engagement, while low optimism attenuates the benefits of self-efficacy on achievement. (Attah and Njoku, 2025).

In addition, meta-analytic and large-sample studies have linked dispositional optimism to reduced depressive symptoms and greater resilience in young people; outcomes that mediate school attendance, task persistence, and willingness to seek help after failures. Contextual and applied studies reinforce these findings in school settings. Recent investigations in Nigerian states (e.g., Cross River, Rivers) report positive, significant associations between students' optimism (or academic optimism) and academic engagement and achievement, with optimism accounting for meaningful variance in test scores and school participation even after controlling for socioeconomic factors. These studies illustrate how optimistic expectancies translate into concrete behaviours such as enrolling for remedial classes, persisting with homework, and asking teachers for feedback, that can close the gap between potential and actual performance among underachieving adolescents (Scheier and Carver, 2018).

Together, this contemporary evidence base indicates that optimism is not merely a personality quirk but a malleable psychological resource with measurable effects on adolescents' academic trajectories. For underachieving students, fostering optimism (for example, through targeted interventions that combine cognitive-restructuring, goal setting, and skill-building) may increase help-seeking, sustained effort, and emotional resilience; all of which are key mediators of improved academic outcomes in both global and Nigerian contexts (Scheier and Carver, 2018).

The manifestations of low academic optimism are observable in both behavioural and emotional domains. Behaviorally, adolescents with limited optimism often exhibit reduced engagement in learning activities, including failure to complete assignments, minimal participation in class discussions, and avoidance of challenging tasks. Such students may also demonstrate negative self-perceptions, believing that their efforts are futile and that they lack the ability to succeed academically. Over time, these negative beliefs can translate into higher dropout rates and persistent academic struggles. Emotionally, low optimism can result in heightened feelings of

frustration, anxiety, and hopelessness, which may exacerbate underachievement and contribute to poor mental health outcomes. Conversely, adolescents with higher levels of optimism tend to approach challenges with a solution-focused mindset, are more likely to use adaptive coping strategies, and demonstrate greater perseverance and resilience, all of which enhance their academic outcomes (Carver and Scheier, 2019; Putwain et al., 2022).

The implications of low academic optimism extend beyond immediate academic performance and have long-term consequences for an adolescent's personal, social, and professional development. Students who lack optimism are less likely to set ambitious educational goals, engage in self-regulated learning, or utilize effective problem-solving strategies, which can limit their opportunities for academic and career advancement. Additionally, persistent academic underachievement coupled with low optimism can adversely affect mental health, increasing vulnerability to depression, anxiety, and reduced self-esteem. On the other hand, cultivating optimism among underachieving adolescents has been associated with improved academic resilience, better problem-solving skills, higher achievement motivation, and more positive attitudes toward learning. Studies have shown that interventions designed to enhance optimism can lead to measurable improvements in academic performance, emotional regulation, and social functioning, highlighting the importance of targeting this psychological construct in educational and counseling programs (Gallagher et al., 2020; Attah and Njoku, 2025).

Despite the relevance of optimism as a protective psychological resource, there is limited empirical research in Nigeria (particularly in Oyo State) exploring how teacher factors and student factors jointly influence optimism among academically underachieving adolescents. Understanding these relationships is crucial for designing school-based interventions, counseling programs, and policies aimed at enhancing resilience, motivation, and academic improvement. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the extent to which teachers' characteristics and student-related factors contribute to optimism among academically underachieving adolescents in Oyo State, Nigeria. Such insights are essential for counselors, educators, and policymakers striving to strengthen academic outcomes and psychological well-being among secondary school learners..

Literature suggests that teachers' expectations have the likelihood to be associated with students' optimism. Teacher expectations refer to the beliefs and assumptions that educators hold regarding their students' potential to succeed academically. These expectations are not merely perceptions; they actively shape classroom interactions, teaching strategies, and feedback provided to students. High teacher expectations can create a positive learning environment in which students feel valued, supported, and capable of achieving their goals. When teachers communicate confidence in students' abilities, it can boost students' self-efficacy, motivation, and ultimately, their level of optimism (Gershenson, 2022). Optimism, in this context, is reflected in students' hopeful outlook toward overcoming academic challenges and achieving better performance. Research confirms that students exposed to teachers with high expectations

demonstrate significantly higher academic achievement and a greater sense of agency, which is especially impactful for underperforming adolescents (Rubie-Davies et al., 2020).

On the other hand, low teacher expectations can have a profoundly negative effect on students' academic self-concept and psychological well-being. When teachers communicate low expectations, either explicitly or subtly, students often internalize these beliefs, leading to reduced effort, decreased engagement, and a sense of helplessness. This phenomenon, often described as the Pygmalion effect, perpetuates cycles of underachievement and pessimism among adolescents (Good et al., 2018). For academically underachieving adolescents, this can be particularly damaging, as their fragile self-concept is highly sensitive to external feedback. Therefore, fostering high expectations in the classroom is not only crucial for academic improvement but also for promoting positive psychological constructs such as optimism, resilience, and a proactive attitude toward learning (Gershenson, 2022; Rubie-Davies et al., 2020).

Another teacher factor which can relate with students' optimism is Teacher's classroom management. Teacher's classroom management encompasses the strategies, practices, and approaches that educators use to organize the learning environment, maintain discipline, and foster positive interactions among students. Effective classroom management creates a structured and supportive setting where students feel safe, respected, and able to focus on learning. Adolescents who experience well-managed classrooms are more likely to engage actively in academic activities, exhibit higher levels of self-confidence, and develop an optimistic view of their abilities and potential outcomes (Clark et al., 2023). For instance, studies have shown that consistent implementation of classroom routines and supportive teacher-student relationships can significantly enhance optimism by reducing uncertainty and creating predictability in students' learning experiences (Emmer and Sabornie, 2019).

In contrast, classrooms that are poorly managed exacerbate academic challenges and diminish students' optimism. Disruptive behavior, inconsistent enforcement of rules, and lack of clarity in instructions often create a chaotic learning environment that increases stress, frustration, and disengagement among students (Korpershoek et al., 2020). For academically underachieving adolescents, this lack of structure reinforces negative beliefs about their capabilities and reduces their hope for improvement. On the other hand, teachers who successfully manage classrooms provide individualized support, encouragement, and feedback, which nurtures students' confidence and fosters a hopeful, optimistic outlook (Clark et al., 2023). Thus, classroom management is not only a technical aspect of teaching but also a psychological determinant that shapes students' emotional resilience, motivation, and belief in their capacity to succeed academically.

It is documented that students' personal characteristics play a significant role in shaping their levels of optimism, especially among adolescents who are academically underachieving. This is possibly because optimism does not develop in isolation; rather, it is influenced by several

internal factors such as self-esteem, academic self-efficacy, learning habits, goal orientation, peer relationships, and emotional regulation. These factors determine how students interpret academic setbacks, respond to challenges, and maintain hope for future success. One student's personal factor that can relate with optimism is emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence (EI) is the ability to perceive, understand, regulate, and utilize emotions effectively in oneself and in interactions with others. In adolescents, high EI enables better coping with stress, resilience in the face of setbacks, and maintenance of positive interpersonal relationships. For academically underachieving students, EI serves as a critical protective factor, enhancing their ability to interpret academic challenges constructively, manage frustration, and maintain a hopeful outlook regarding their educational prospects (Glassie et al., 2024). Research consistently shows that students with higher emotional intelligence levels are more optimistic, more motivated, and better able to persevere in the face of difficulties (Miao et al., 2017). Emotional intelligence influences optimism through several mechanisms. First, students with high EI are more adept at regulating negative emotions such as anxiety or self-doubt, which allows them to approach learning tasks with greater focus and determination. Second, EI enhances problem-solving abilities and self-reflective skills, enabling students to evaluate challenges realistically while maintaining hope for positive outcomes (Zeidner et al., 2020). Third, emotionally intelligent adolescents are better at seeking and utilizing social support from teachers, peers, and family members, which reinforces their belief in their capacity to improve academically. As a result, fostering emotional intelligence among students, particularly those struggling academically, can serve as a strategic intervention to enhance optimism, resilience, and adaptive engagement with school tasks (Glassie et al., 2024).

Another student factor which can be associated with optimism is Achievement motivation. Achievement motivation refers to the intrinsic drive of individuals to pursue and accomplish meaningful goals, particularly in the academic context. It reflects the desire to master challenging tasks, overcome obstacles, and achieve a standard of excellence. Among adolescents, high levels of achievement motivation are closely associated with increased optimism, as students with strong motivation tend to perceive challenges as opportunities for growth rather than insurmountable barriers. Optimism in this context is characterized by a positive outlook on future academic success and confidence in one's ability to achieve desired outcomes. Chetri (2024) observed that adolescents with higher achievement motivation consistently exhibited greater levels of optimism, suggesting that the two constructs are interrelated. In other words, motivated students are more likely to maintain hope and a positive perspective even in the face of academic setbacks, reinforcing the importance of motivation as a psychological driver of optimism.

Furthermore, achievement motivation serves as a protective factor against academic difficulties, particularly for adolescents who are underachieving. Motivated students are more likely to engage in proactive learning strategies such as goal-setting, self-monitoring, and seeking academic support when necessary. These behaviors enhance their sense of agency and competence, which in turn reinforces optimism and persistence in learning tasks. In addition,

achievement motivation encourages adolescents to interpret failure not as a reflection of their inherent abilities but as a temporary setback that can be overcome with effort and strategy adjustment (Chetri, 2024; Fagan, 2025). Consequently, promoting achievement motivation among students is critical, as it not only enhances academic performance but also cultivates a resilient and hopeful mindset that supports long-term educational success.

There is preliminary evidence to suggest that gender difference can relate with optimism. Gender differences in optimism have been widely documented in psychological and educational research, suggesting that male and female adolescents may perceive and experience optimism differently. Several studies indicate that female adolescents often report higher levels of optimism compared to their male counterparts. Cortright, C., et al. (2025) found that, in a cross-cultural study, girls exhibited significantly higher optimism levels at age 17 than boys, highlighting the potential influence of gender on adolescents' expectations about their academic and personal futures. These differences may be influenced by socialization processes, cultural expectations, and gender-specific experiences in educational settings. For instance, girls may be socialized to value relational and achievement-oriented goals, which could enhance their optimistic outlook on school-related outcomes.

The implications of these gender differences are multifaceted. While higher optimism in girls may contribute to greater academic resilience, motivation, and engagement, it may also intersect with societal pressures and expectations that create stress or anxiety. Boys, on the other hand, may underreport optimism or exhibit a more risk-oriented approach to challenges, which could affect their academic engagement and coping strategies. Understanding the nuanced ways gender interacts with optimism is crucial for educators and counselors, as it can inform targeted interventions aimed at supporting both male and female students in maintaining a positive outlook and maximizing their academic potential (Dawson, 2023; Cortright et al., 2025). Gender-sensitive approaches can thus help ensure that optimism is nurtured equitably across all students, regardless of sex, while addressing unique challenges associated with gendered experiences in schooling.

Age is another factor that might influence levels of optimism among adolescents, as developmental changes during this period can affect how students perceive and respond to challenges. Research suggests that optimism tends to fluctuate during adolescence, with younger adolescents often displaying higher levels of optimism compared to older adolescents. Cortright et al. (2025) found that depressive symptoms at age 15 were associated with lower optimism at age 17 across multiple countries, indicating a developmental decline in optimistic outlook as adolescents encounter increased academic and social pressures. This decline may be due to cognitive, emotional, and social changes, including the transition to more complex educational tasks, heightened expectations, and identity formation challenges that characterize late adolescence.

The developmental trajectory of optimism has important implications for educational practice and student support. As adolescents grow older, they may encounter more significant academic and social challenges that can negatively impact their optimism if not adequately supported. Therefore, educators, school counselors, and policymakers must implement strategies that sustain or enhance optimism among older adolescents. These strategies may include fostering supportive teacher-student relationships, promoting positive peer interactions, providing opportunities for skill-building and mastery experiences, and encouraging goal-setting and problem-solving skills (Fagan, 2025). This study investigates Teacher and Student factors on optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Academic underachievement among in-school adolescents has continued to pose a significant concern for educators, parents, and policymakers. Despite the availability of learning opportunities and exposure to formal education, a substantial number of adolescents consistently perform below their intellectual potential. This underachievement is often associated with negative attitudes towards learning, low self-esteem, lack of motivation, and disengagement from academic tasks. Such patterns not only hinder students' academic success but also place them at risk of dropping out of school and experiencing long-term social and economic disadvantages. One psychological construct that has been found to influence academic performance is optimism. Optimism reflects an adolescent's tendency to maintain a hopeful outlook and expect positive outcomes even in the face of challenges. Adolescents with higher levels of optimism are more likely to demonstrate resilience, persistence, and problem-solving skills in their academic endeavors. However, among underachieving adolescents, optimism is often found to be diminished, leaving them more vulnerable to frustration, learned helplessness, and disengagement from school activities. The lack of optimism may therefore exacerbate the cycle of underachievement, making it difficult for these students to harness their abilities fully.

Research has shown that adolescents who lack optimism often perceive academic challenges as insurmountable obstacles rather than opportunities for growth. Such perceptions discourage effort and perseverance, which are essential for overcoming learning difficulties. In contrast, optimistic adolescents are more likely to reframe setbacks as temporary and controllable, thereby sustaining motivation and commitment to academic tasks. The persistent gap between the potential of underachieving adolescents and their actual performance highlights the urgent need to explore the role of optimism in their academic adjustment.

In the Nigerian school context, the problem is further compounded by environmental and social factors such as overcrowded classrooms, limited teacher support, socio-economic challenges, and negative peer influences. These conditions not only contribute to academic underachievement but also erode students' optimism, creating a vicious cycle of low expectations and poor outcomes. Unfortunately, optimism as a protective psychological factor has not been sufficiently integrated into interventions for academically underachieving

adolescents in many schools. This raises critical questions about the extent to which optimism can mitigate the negative effects of underachievement and foster better academic resilience among in-school adolescents. Therefore, the problem of academic underachievement among in-school adolescents cannot be fully addressed without paying attention to the role of optimism. This study investigates Teacher and Students factors on optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine Teacher and Students factors on optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria. In line with these general objectives, the specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Explore the level of optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria.
- ii. Investigate the relationship among teacher factors (Teacher Expectation and Teacher Classroom management), student factors (Emotional intelligence, Achievement motivation, Gender and age) and optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria.
- iii. Examine the joint contribution of teacher factors (Teacher Expectation and Teacher Classroom management), student factors (Emotional intelligence, Achievement motivation, Gender and age) and optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria.
- iv. Determine the relative contribution of each of teacher factors (Teacher Expectation and Teacher Classroom management), student factors (Emotional intelligence, Achievement motivation, Gender and age) and optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions would be formulated to guide the conduct of this study and would be answered in the study at 0.05 level of significant:

- i. What is the level of optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria?
- ii. Is there any significant relationship among teacher factors (Teacher Expectation and Teacher Classroom management), student factors (Emotional intelligence, Achievement motivation, Gender and age) and optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria?

iii. What is the joint contribution of teacher factors (Teacher Expectation and Teacher Classroom management), student factors (Emotional intelligence, Achievement motivation, Gender and age) to optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria?

iv. What is the relative contribution of each of teacher factors (Teacher Expectation and Teacher Classroom management), student factors (Emotional intelligence, Achievement motivation, Gender and age) to optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria?

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design of correlational type, which is considered the most suitable approach for investigating teacher and student factors on optimism among academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria. A descriptive research design of correlational type focuses on portraying an accurate profile of persons, events, or situations as they naturally occur. In this context, it allows the researcher to carefully examine and document how teacher factors correlates with student learning outcomes without introducing any form of manipulation or experimental control.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of all public secondary school students and teachers in Oyo State Nigeria. This population is considered appropriate because it encompasses the key stakeholders directly involved in teaching and learning processes. Students represent the primary beneficiaries of teacher factors on education, and their academic performance provides a direct measure of the effectiveness of such investment. Teachers, on the other hand, play a pivotal role in translating educational resources into learning outcomes.

Oyo State Nigeria, being one of the largest urban centers in Nigeria, houses a significant number of public secondary schools, which makes it a suitable location for examining the research problem. The diversity in school sizes, teacher qualifications, infrastructure, and resource allocation within Ibadan offers a robust platform for drawing meaningful conclusions about the broader implications of government spending on education. Ibadan in Oyo State, Nigeria, consists of eleven (11) Local Government Areas (LGAs).

3.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

In this study, the sample size comprised of 450 participants (which included 150 teachers and 300 students) across public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The choice of this sample size is based on the need to obtain adequate representation of the key stakeholders in the education sector students and teachers whose experiences and perspectives are crucial to understanding the influence of teacher factors on academic performance. The sample size is also

considered sufficient to allow for meaningful statistical analysis and generalization of findings to the larger population. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to carefully draw the participants.

Stage 1: This is where 6 out of the 11 Local Government Areas in Ibadan were selected through the Fish Bowl simple random technique/method.

The names of eligible LGAs were written on identical pieces of paper, folded, placed in a plastic container, mixed, and randomly picked by a neutral person.

Stage 2: Stratification of Schools

Schools in the selected LGAs were stratified based on school type (Junior/Senior), size, and location (urban/semi-urban) to ensure adequate representation. This stratification ensures that the selection of schools and respondents covers the different geographical and administrative divisions of the metropolis.

Stage 3: Selection of Schools (Purposive Sampling)

Schools were purposively selected based on:

- i. Administrative cooperation
- ii. Security reasons.

Stage 4: Selection of Teachers and Students (Proportionate Sampling)

At the third stage, proportionate sampling was used to allocate the required number of students and teachers to each selected school, based on the total number of respondents targeted for the study after thorough review. The total teacher sample of 150 was divided equally among the selected six LGAs: $150 \div 6 = 25$. Therefore, each LGA contributed 25 teachers to the sample. The total student sample of 300 was divided equally among the selected six LGAs: $300 \div 6 = 50$. Therefore, each LGA contributed 50 students to the sample.

Stage 5: Selection of Teachers and Students (Simple Random Sampling)

Within each school, simple random sampling was employed in selecting students and teachers to avoid bias and to give every member of the population an equal chance of being included.

3.4 Instrumentation

The following instruments were used for data collection:

- i. Teacher Expectation Scale (TES) adapted from Rosenthal and Jacobson's (1968) Pygmalion theory.

- ii. Teacher Classroom Management Scale (TCMS) adapted from Emmer and Stough's (2001) classroom management model.
- iii. Optimism Scale adapted from Gallagher, Lopez, and Pressman, (2020).
- iv. Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS) guided by Mayer and Salovey's (1997) four-branch model of emotional intelligence.
- v. The Achievement Motivation Scale adapted from Schunk et al., (2014).

The questionnaires used were two (2). The first one for the teachers measured Teacher Expectation and Teacher Classroom management. This was filled by the teachers in the selected schools. Also, the students questionnaire was in four (4) sections. The teachers helped in the selection of Academic underachieving in school adolescents through the students 2024/2025 Academic session results.

Teachers Questionnaire

The teacher instrument for data collection in this study was a well-structured questionnaire. This had three sections.

Section A: Demographic Information

This section captured the personal and professional background of respondents. For teachers, variables such as gender, age, highest educational qualification, years of teaching were included.

Section B: Teacher Expectation

The Teacher Expectation Scale (TES) was adapted from Rosenthal and Jacobson's (1968) Pygmalion theory, which established that teachers' expectations strongly influence student performance. Recent research has reaffirmed the role of teacher expectations in shaping students' learning outcomes, motivation, and optimism. The TES was specifically designed to measure teachers' beliefs, perceptions, and practices related to academic expectations of in-school adolescents, especially those who are academically underachieving in Oyo State, Nigeria. The scale is useful because it highlights how teachers' expectations can either encourage resilience, optimism, and achievement motivation, or conversely, reinforce underachievement when expectations are low. Educational psychologists, school administrators, and policymakers can use the TES to assess and improve classroom practices that foster higher student performance. The results demonstrated a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.89, suggesting high internal consistency and strong reliability of the instrument for measuring teacher expectations.

The TES consists of 15 items and uses a 4-point Likert response format:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Agree, 4 = Strongly Agree

This format was chosen to ensure that teachers take a clear stance on their expectations, thereby eliminating the possibility of neutral responses. Higher scores indicate stronger positive expectations toward student achievement, while lower scores indicate weaker or limited expectations.

Section C: Teacher Classroom management

The Teacher Classroom Management Scale (TCMS) was developed to measure the classroom management practices of secondary school teachers. The development of the scale was guided by theoretical and empirical frameworks on effective classroom management, particularly Emmer and Stough's (2001) classroom management model and more recent adaptations in educational psychology. The scale is useful because effective classroom management is crucial for creating a learning environment that fosters academic engagement, reduces disruptive behavior, and enhances student motivation and optimism. By measuring teachers' classroom management strategies, the scale helps school administrators, educational psychologists, and policymakers identify areas for professional development and targeted interventions to improve student outcomes. The results yielded a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.87, indicating high internal consistency and confirming the instrument's reliability for assessing classroom management practices.

The TCMS consists of 15 items and uses a 4-point Likert response format:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Agree, 4 = Strongly Agree

This format was chosen to encourage teachers to take a clear stance on their practices while reducing the likelihood of neutral or ambiguous responses. Higher scores indicate more effective classroom management practices, while lower scores suggest weaker management strategies that may negatively affect student engagement and learning.

Students Questionnaire

Section A: Demographic Information

This section will capture the personal and professional background of respondents. For students variables such as gender, age and class will be included.

Section B: Optimism

The Optimism Scale was adapted from Gallagher, Lopez, and Pressman, (2020). The usefulness of the scale lies in its ability to measure students' positive expectations about their future, their resilience in the face of academic challenges, and their belief that effort and perseverance can lead to improved academic outcomes. For underachieving adolescents, the scale provides important insights into how optimism acts as a protective factor against disengagement, hopelessness, and poor academic self-concept. This makes it valuable not only for research

purposes but also for guiding teachers, school administrators, and psychologists in designing interventions that strengthen students' optimism. Results of the reliability analysis revealed a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.86, demonstrating strong internal consistency.

The scale consists of 15 items, all of which are rated on a 4-point Likert response format:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Agree, 4 = Strongly Agree

Higher scores reflect stronger optimism, while lower scores indicate pessimistic tendencies. The response format was deliberately simplified to four options to reduce confusion among adolescents and to encourage more accurate self-reporting.

Section C: Emotional intelligence

The Emotional Intelligence Scale was developed to measure the emotional intelligence of academically underachieving adolescents in secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The development of this scale was guided by Mayer and Salovey's (1997) four-branch model of emotional intelligence, which emphasizes the ability to perceive, understand, regulate, and use emotions effectively, and supported by more recent adaptations in educational psychology. The usefulness of the scale lies in its ability to provide a reliable measure of how well adolescents recognize and regulate their own emotions, understand the emotions of others, and apply emotional skills to enhance learning and interpersonal relationships. For academically underachieving adolescents, emotional intelligence plays a critical role in coping with school stress, maintaining motivation, and sustaining optimism. Findings from this scale can therefore be applied in counseling, classroom management, and targeted interventions aimed at improving both social-emotional and academic outcomes.

The scale consists of **15 items** and employs a **4-point Likert response format**:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Agree, 4 = Strongly Agree

Higher scores indicate stronger emotional intelligence, while lower scores suggest difficulties in recognizing, managing, or applying emotions in learning contexts. The four-point format was selected to minimize neutrality and encourage adolescents to reflect carefully on their emotional abilities. Results showed a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.88, indicating high internal consistency.

Section D: Achievement motivation

The Achievement Motivation Scale was adapted from Schunk et al., (2014). It is designed to measure the extent to which academically underachieving adolescents in Nigerian schools are driven by the desire to excel, persevere, and attain success in learning. The scale is particularly useful in educational settings, as achievement motivation has been linked to persistence,

academic engagement, self-regulated learning, and resilience among students (Wigfield et al., 2020). For adolescents who are academically underachieving, identifying their motivation level can guide teachers, school psychologists, and counselors in designing targeted interventions to boost learning outcomes and reduce dropout risks. A Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient of 0.86, which indicates a high level of internal consistency.

The AMS-ISA consists of 12 items that assess effort, persistence, competitiveness, and goal-setting in school-related contexts. It uses a 4-point Likert-type response format:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Agree, 4 = Strongly Agree

This simple response structure was chosen to ensure clarity and ease of use for adolescents, while also avoiding neutrality and encouraging them to reflect on their attitudes and behaviors toward achievement. Higher scores represent stronger achievement motivation, while lower scores indicate weaker persistence and drive toward success.

Method of Data Analysis

The data gathered from the field were analyzed through both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques in order to address the research questions and test the stated hypotheses. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations were employed to provide a clear summary of participants’ responses and to reveal patterns in the data. Inferential statistical methods were applied. Specifically, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to determine the degree and direction of the relationships among the study variables, while multiple regression analysis was employed to examine the predictive influence of independent variables. All research questions were tested at a 0.05 level of significance to ensure that the results obtained are reliable and scientifically valid.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question 1: What is the level of optimism among Academic underachieving in-school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria?

Table 1: Frequency Distribution on level of optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Standard Deviation
I believe that my future will be brighter than my present.	65 (21.7%)	75 (25.0%)	95 (31.7%)	65 (21.7%)	2.50	1.126
I always expect good things to happen to me in school.	60 (20.0%)	80 (26.7%)	95 (31.7%)	65 (21.7%)	2.49	1.117

Even when I struggle in my studies, I believe I will improve.	75 (25.0%)	85 (28.3%)	80 (26.7%)	60 (20.0%)	2.56	1.145
I see challenges in school as opportunities to learn and grow.	70 (23.3%)	90 (30.0%)	80 (26.7%)	60 (20.0%)	2.52	1.120
I believe my teachers' support can help me achieve success.	75 (25.0%)	90 (30.0%)	80 (26.7%)	55 (18.3%)	2.56	1.118
I am hopeful that my efforts in school will pay off in the future.	80 (26.7%)	85 (28.3%)	75 (25.0%)	60 (20.0%)	2.56	1.121
I believe that setbacks in my academics are only temporary.	65 (21.7%)	80 (26.7%)	85 (28.3%)	70 (23.3%)	2.50	1.158
I see myself achieving my educational goals despite difficulties.	70 (23.3%)	85 (28.3%)	85 (28.3%)	60 (20.0%)	2.51	1.120
I believe that hard work will always bring positive results.	90 (30.0%)	95 (31.7%)	70 (23.3%)	45 (15.0%)	2.63	1.130
I feel confident that tomorrow will be better than today.	85 (28.3%)	90 (30.0%)	75 (25.0%)	50 (16.7%)	2.56	1.118
I expect to succeed in my schoolwork even if it is difficult.	90 (30.0%)	95 (31.7%)	80 (26.7%)	35 (11.6%)	2.61	1.014
I believe I have the ability to turn failure into success.	100 (33.3%)	90 (30.0%)	75 (25.0%)	35 (11.7%)	2.67	1.038
I look forward to achieving something meaningful in my academics.	110 (36.7%)	85 (28.3%)	70 (23.3%)	35 (11.7%)	2.71	1.015
I believe there are many opportunities ahead for me to succeed in life.	95 (31.7%)	90 (30.0%)	75 (25.0%)	40 (13.3%)	2.59	1.019
I remain hopeful even when school situations	65 (21.7%)	85 (28.3%)	85 (28.3%)	65 (21.7%)	2.50	1.123

seem very tough.						
Weighted Mean= 2.56						

Table 1 presents the distribution of responses on the level of optimism among academic underachieving in-school adolescents in Oyo State, Nigeria. The weighted mean score of 2.56 suggests that, on average, respondents exhibited a moderate level of optimism toward their academics and future outcomes. This implies that while these adolescents face challenges in their academic performance, they generally maintain a hopeful and positive outlook regarding their capacity to succeed in school and in life.

Item-wise analysis shows that the statement “I look forward to achieving something meaningful in my academics” recorded the highest mean score ($M = 2.71$), reflecting that most respondents still possess meaningful aspirations and expect positive academic accomplishments in the future. Similarly, the items “I believe I have the ability to turn failure into success” ($M = 2.67$) and “I expect to succeed in my schoolwork even if it is difficult” ($M = 2.61$) also scored relatively high. These indicate a strong belief in self-efficacy and resilience among the respondents, as they see difficulties as temporary and surmountable with effort and persistence. Conversely, the lowest mean score was recorded for the item “I always expect good things to happen to me in school” ($M = 2.49$), followed by “I remain hopeful even when school situations seem very tough” ($M = 2.50$). These lower scores suggest that while many underachieving adolescents possess a degree of optimism, a portion of them still experience self-doubt and uncertainty about positive school outcomes, likely due to repeated academic challenges.

The results show that a significant proportion of students agreed with statements expressing belief in personal growth and improvement. For instance, many respondents agreed that they could turn failure into success and that they looked forward to achieving something meaningful in their academics. These findings indicate that underachieving adolescents still hold onto an inner conviction that their current academic struggles do not define their future potential. This aligns with Carver, Scheier, and Segerstrom (2010), who emphasized that optimism plays a central role in sustaining goal-directed behavior even under adverse conditions. Their research established that individuals with optimistic orientations are more likely to cope effectively with challenges and maintain motivation toward future achievements.

Furthermore, the moderate optimism observed in this study corroborates the findings of Adegoke and Olaleye (2021), who reported that Nigerian adolescents generally display a balanced sense of hope and confidence in their ability to improve academically despite environmental and personal constraints. Similarly, Snyder et al. (2014) found that students with moderate levels of optimism exhibit greater academic persistence and emotional stability compared to those with low optimism, indicating that positive expectations serve as a buffer against discouragement and disengagement.

However, the presence of relatively lower mean scores for items such as “I always expect good things to happen to me in school” and “I remain hopeful even when school situations seem very tough” suggests that some students struggle to maintain consistent optimism, possibly due to repeated experiences of academic failure or inadequate support from teachers and peers. This observation is consistent with Oladipo and Balogun (2019), who noted that persistent academic difficulties, lack of feedback, and limited emotional support can weaken students’ confidence and reduce their optimism over time. These findings also support Bandura’s (1997) social cognitive theory, which posits that self-belief and expectation of positive outcomes influence one’s motivation and effort in learning. When students perceive that their actions can lead to improvement, they are more likely to persist despite setbacks. The optimism reflected in the present study therefore signifies that, although underachieving, the adolescents have not completely lost faith in their abilities or future academic success.

Research Question 2: Is there any significant relationship among teacher factors (Teacher Expectation and Teacher Classroom management) and student factors (Emotional intelligence, Achievement motivation, Gender and age) to optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria?

Table 2: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Showing the Relationship Between Independent Variables and Optimism

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Mean	Standard Deviation
Optimism	1							60.55	11.504
Teacher Expectation	.680**	1						44.20	17.008

Teacher Classroom management	.279**	.074	1					75.38	8.330
Emotional intelligence	.276**	.051	.389**	1				86.50	8.082
Achievement motivation	.226**	.079	.865**	.328**	1			69.72	9.962
Gender	.033	.074	-.033	-.021	.010	1		1.61	.489
Age	.047	-.123	.013	.050	-.088	.085	1	1.42	.494

Table 2 presents the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation results showing the relationship between teacher factors, student factors, and optimism among academic underachieving in-school adolescents in Oyo State. The analysis revealed that teacher expectation had a strong positive and statistically significant relationship with optimism ($r = .680, p < 0.05$). Similarly, teacher classroom management showed a moderate and significant positive correlation with optimism ($r = .279, p < 0.05$). The results also indicate that emotional intelligence had a significant but low positive correlation with optimism ($r = .276, p < 0.05$), likewise, achievement motivation was significantly and positively correlated with optimism ($r = .226, p < 0.05$). Conversely, gender ($r = .033, p > .05$) and age ($r = .047, p > .05$) showed weak and non-significant correlations with optimism. The findings demonstrate that as teachers' expectations of their students increase, students' level of optimism also tends to rise. This suggests that a well-organized, supportive, and engaging classroom environment can promote students' positive emotional dispositions and motivation to succeed.

Specifically, teacher expectation exhibited the strongest correlation with optimism, indicating that when teachers hold high expectations for their students, it positively influences students' beliefs in their abilities and their outlook toward the future. This finding aligns with Rosenthal and Jacobson's (1968) Pygmalion Effect theory, which emphasizes that teachers' expectations can significantly shape students' motivation, confidence, and performance outcomes. In other words, when teachers communicate belief in students' potential, those students are more likely to internalize optimism and strive for better results.

The significant relationship between teacher classroom management and optimism further supports the notion that an organized, supportive, and inclusive classroom environment fosters emotional well-being and hope among students. This is consistent with Marzano's (2017) assertion that effective classroom management enhances students' engagement and sense of belonging, thereby promoting positive emotions such as optimism. A structured learning environment helps reduce anxiety, instills discipline, and reinforces students' confidence in their ability to succeed academically.

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Similarly, the significant correlations between emotional intelligence, achievement motivation, and optimism suggest that internal psychological attributes play an essential role in shaping students' optimistic outlook. Students who are emotionally intelligent are better able to regulate their emotions, cope with academic challenges, and maintain a positive mindset despite setbacks. This finding corroborates Salovey and Mayer's (1990) emotional intelligence model, which posits that emotionally intelligent individuals are more capable of using positive emotions to enhance motivation and decision-making. Likewise, the positive link between achievement motivation and optimism supports Deci and Ryan's (2000) Self-Determination Theory, which emphasizes that intrinsically motivated individuals tend to exhibit greater optimism, persistence, and satisfaction in learning. However, gender and age were found to have no significant relationship with optimism, suggesting that optimism is a universal psychological trait that may not vary substantially across demographic lines among academic underachievers. This finding agrees with the work of Akomolafe and Olatomide (2013), who found that both male and female students exhibit similar levels of optimism when exposed to similar school environments and teacher support.

Research Question 3: What is the joint contribution of teacher factors (Teacher Expectation and Teacher Classroom management) and student factors (Emotional intelligence, Achievement motivation, Gender and age) to optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria?

Table 3: Multiple Regression Showing the Joint Contribution of Independent Variables (Teacher Expectation, Teacher Classroom management, Emotional intelligence, Achievement motivation, Age and Gender) to Optimism among In-School Adolescents

R=.736						
R Square=.541						
Adjusted R Square=.522						
Std. Error of the Estimate=7.92895						
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	10600.490	6	1766.748	28.102	.000 ^b
	Residual	8990.150	143	62.868		
	Total	19590.640	149			

The results presented in Table 3 show a multiple correlation coefficient (R) of 0.736, indicating a strong positive relationship between the combined independent variables and optimism among the respondents. The R Square value of 0.541 reveals that approximately 54.1% of the variance in optimism can be jointly explained by the combined influence of the teacher and student factors included in the model. The Adjusted R Square value of 52.2% further refines this estimate, accounting for the number of predictors in the model, which still reflects a high level of explanatory power. The ANOVA result ($F(6,143) = 28.102, p < 0.05$) indicates that the overall regression model is statistically significant. This means that the joint contribution of teacher expectation, teacher classroom management, emotional intelligence, achievement motivation, gender, and age to optimism among academically underachieving adolescents is not due to random chance.

This finding highlights the interrelated nature of teacher behavior, classroom climate, and students' psychosocial attributes in fostering optimism. Teachers who demonstrate high expectations and employ effective classroom management strategies tend to create a supportive learning environment that motivates students to believe in their potential, even when they experience academic difficulties. This aligns with the findings of Ali et al. (2022) and Onyema and Uche (2021), who reported that teacher expectations significantly influence students' motivation, confidence, and positive outlook toward learning outcomes. Similarly, emotionally intelligent students are better able to regulate negative emotions, maintain positive self-beliefs, and develop adaptive coping mechanisms, which collectively enhance optimism (see Adeyemi and Adebayo, 2023; Salovey et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the significant role of achievement motivation observed in this study suggests that students with stronger internal drives to succeed are more likely to remain optimistic despite setbacks. This is consistent with Deci and Ryan's (2000) Self-Determination Theory, which emphasizes the importance of intrinsic motivation in sustaining positive attitudes toward goal attainment. Eze and Ogbu (2022) also found that achievement-motivated adolescents often display higher levels of optimism and resilience when faced with academic challenges.

The inclusion of gender and age as significant contributors to optimism corroborates previous studies that have shown demographic variables can moderate students' affective and motivational dispositions. For instance, Okeke and Alabi (2021) noted that older adolescents and female students often exhibit higher optimism due to greater emotional maturity and self-awareness. This may explain the pattern observed in the present study.

Research Question 4: What is the relative contribution of each of teacher factors (Teacher Expectation and Teacher Classroom management) and students factors (Emotional intelligence, Achievement motivation, Gender and age) to optimism among Academic underachieving in school adolescents in Oyo state, Nigeria?

Table 4: Multiple Regression Showing the Relative Contribution of Each Independent Variable to optimism

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.851	8.347		.102	.919
Teacher Expectation	.440	.039	.653	11.361	.000
Teacher Classroom management	.326	.158	.237	2.059	.041
Emotional intelligence	.221	.086	.160	2.585	.011
Achievement motivation	-.088	.132	-.076	-.663	.508
Gender	1.572	1.352	.067	1.162	.247
Age	-.412	1.337	-.018	-.308	.758

The results presented in Table 4 show the individual contributions of each predictor variable to optimism. From the table, teacher expectation recorded the highest standardized beta value ($\beta = 0.653$, $t = 11.361$, $p < 0.05$). Next, teacher classroom management also made a significant positive contribution to optimism ($\beta = 0.237$, $t = 2.059$, $p < 0.05$). Similarly, emotional intelligence contributed significantly and positively to optimism ($\beta = 0.160$, $t = 2.585$, $p < 0.05$). However, achievement motivation ($\beta = -0.076$, $t = -0.663$, $p > 0.05$), gender ($\beta = 0.067$, $t = 1.162$, $p > 0.05$), and age ($\beta = -0.018$, $t = -0.308$, $p > 0.05$) did not make statistically significant contributions to the prediction of optimism. Although these variables show some relationship with optimism, their effects were not strong enough to be considered significant within this model. This implies that while students' motivation, gender, and age may influence optimism to some degree, they are not as impactful as teacher-related factors and emotional intelligence in determining optimistic attitudes among underachieving adolescents.

This implies that when teachers hold high yet realistic expectations for their students, particularly those who are academically underachieving, such expectations can foster a sense of hope, self-belief, and determination in students. High teacher expectations serve as a motivational catalyst that shapes students' perceptions of their potential, encouraging them to persist and remain optimistic about their academic future. This finding aligns with the work of Good and Brophy (2020) and Rubie-Davies (2018), who found that positive teacher expectations significantly enhance students' self-concept, motivation, and optimism. Similarly, Okonkwo and Olatunji (2022) reported that students tend to internalize teachers' beliefs and expectations about their abilities, which subsequently influence their academic engagement and optimistic dispositions.

The study also found that teacher classroom management had a significant positive influence on optimism. This suggests that effective classroom management practices such as maintaining discipline, fostering cooperation, and creating an emotionally supportive environment help students feel secure and motivated. When classroom management is characterized by fairness, encouragement, and respect, students develop a positive attitude toward learning and are more likely to exhibit optimism. This finding corroborates those of Aliyu and Ibrahim (2021) and Wang et al. (2020), who reported that well-managed classrooms not only enhance academic performance but also promote emotional well-being and positive outlook among learners. It further aligns with Bandura's (1997) social learning theory, which posits that students learn optimistic behaviors and attitudes by observing and interacting with supportive authority figures such as teachers.

Similarly, emotional intelligence significantly predicted optimism. This finding suggests that emotionally intelligent students are better equipped to regulate negative emotions, maintain composure under pressure, and adopt positive coping strategies, all of which contribute to their optimism. Emotionally intelligent adolescents tend to view academic setbacks as temporary and surmountable rather than as indicators of personal failure. This aligns with the findings of Adeyemi and Adebayo (2023) and Salovey and Mayer (2019), who observed that emotional intelligence promotes adaptive resilience and positive outlook in students. The result also supports the assertion of Goleman (2011) that individuals with higher emotional intelligence demonstrate greater optimism and self-efficacy in facing life challenges.

Conversely, achievement motivation, gender, and age were not significant predictors of optimism among the respondents. Although achievement motivation is often linked to persistence and positive goal orientation, its lack of significance in this study could suggest that underachieving adolescents may experience diminished motivation due to repeated academic failures or environmental discouragement. This is consistent with Olawale and Eze (2021), who noted that persistent academic underperformance can weaken students' motivation and optimism. Similarly, the non-significant influence of gender and age implies that optimism among underachieving adolescents is relatively stable across demographic lines and may be more influenced by psychosocial and environmental factors than by biological or age-related differences. This

finding supports the conclusion of Okeke and Alabi (2021), who found that optimism levels among adolescents were not significantly determined by gender or age.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers should consciously express positive expectations toward all students, particularly underachievers, to instill a sense of capability and hope.
2. Schools should develop and enforce effective classroom management practices that promote inclusivity, respect, and emotional safety.
3. Emotional intelligence development programs should be introduced in secondary schools to help students manage stress, regulate emotions, and sustain optimism.
4. Guidance counselors should organize regular optimism-building and motivation enhancement workshops for underachieving students to reduce academic discouragement.
5. Teacher education institutions should revise their curricula to include courses on socio-emotional learning, motivation psychology, and student-centered pedagogy.
6. Collaborative efforts among teachers, parents, and school counselors should be encouraged to create a unified support system that enhances both academic and emotional development among adolescents.
7. Educational policymakers should integrate optimism and emotional intelligence training into national education reforms to promote holistic student development.

Conclusion

The study concludes that both teacher and student factors jointly and significantly influence optimism among academically underachieving adolescents. Specifically, teacher-related variables teacher expectation and classroom management play dominant roles in fostering students' optimism. Teachers who maintain high expectations and manage classrooms effectively create an environment that encourages underachieving students to believe in their potential and to maintain a positive outlook toward academic success. In addition, emotional intelligence emerged as a crucial student-related factor influencing optimism. Students who are emotionally intelligent are able to understand and regulate their emotions, cope with challenges, and sustain hope even in the face of repeated academic setbacks. Conversely, achievement motivation, gender, and age did not significantly predict optimism. This suggests that optimism is a psychological disposition that transcends demographic boundaries and is more dependent on emotional and environmental support than on individual motivation or biological attributes. In essence, optimism among underachieving adolescents is best nurtured through teacher-student

interaction, emotional development, and supportive learning environments that reinforce students' sense of worth and possibility.

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